

WHAT IS THE PLACE OF GRAMMAR IN LANGUAGE TEACHING?

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ELSEVIER

Gaukhar Serikbaevna Khaldarchaeva

Senior Teacher of Chirchik State Pedagogical University
Tourism faculty Interfaculty
Department of Foreign languages

Abstract: This article discusses the process of teaching any foreign language that requires all integrated skills, which is constituted vital part of the whole process. So each of them is equally in great demand for teaching English. Grammar is essential and beneficial for not only writers, journalists, and poets, but also for teacher of foreign languages, who are engaged in literary field.

It is known that Grammar is a science which equips us with the powerful communicational abilities and aids. It tells us how to impress people with our speech and conversation. Moreover, it absolutely support a language teacher to conduct his or her lesson effectively. The reason is that without knowing grammar, any individual may come across with difficulties for making a sentence and implementing words in a correct order.

Keywords: language structure, dialect, communicational abilities, implementing words, fundamental subject, linguistic use, ELT setting, significance of language structure information, to illustrate.

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Teaching any foreign language may not seem to be easy as it is believed, because explaining sophisticated thing to learners, whose native language varies quietly from the target language. In the process of teaching any foreign language requires all integrated skill, which is constituted vital part of the whole process. So each of them is equally in great demand for teaching English.

Firstly, before it can be defined to consider the put of linguistic use in English dialect educating; we examine the part of language structure in language. Each dialect has its language structure. The linguistic use of the dialect is imperative. Subsequently, Language structure is essentially concerned with the think about of language. It clarifies to us the challenges and issues included in learning a dialect and it guides us to how dialect is viably utilized in our day-to-day life. Language structure tells us how words are shaped and why they are classified into different categories. It also instructs us how words are combined and grouped into sentences. Grammar makes us familiar with sentence structure. It enables us to comprehend how sentences are patterned and how they are utilized in our practical life for correctly and effective communication.

Grammar is essential and beneficial for not only writers, journalists, and poets, but also for teacher of foreign languages, who are engaged in literary field. It creates proper opportunities for those who wish to perfect their written languages. Grammar is a science which equips us with the powerful communicational abilities

and aids. It tells us how to impress people with our speech and conversation. Moreover, it absolutely support a language teacher to conduct his or her lesson effectively. The reason is that without knowing grammar, any individual may come across with difficulties for making a sentence and implementing words in a correct order. In English dialect instructing, the part of language structure within the learning of English language is still a disputable subject, numerous English language scholars and dialect specialists argued that linguistic use can be utilized as an fundamental subject for learning English in ELT setting. In case we come back, dialect educating strategies, the language structure interpretation strategy is still instructed by many English dialect instructors. Taking after the contention whether to instruct or not to educate linguistic use, it has presently superior realized that the center issue is not on the significance of language structure information but more on how to instruct it. Furthermore, with the help of knowing grammar of the language better, the teaching process may seem easier to conduct, because a tutor can easily teach his or her learners how to make a sentence and implementing word choice in the sentence.

To conclude, as I mentioned above all integrated skill are very crucial and grammar is also very urgent part or substance of the great process, which means with the help of grammar we can enhance other integrated skills easily. A skilled teacher should acquire the grammar of the language, which he or she conduct in the classroom, help teachers to illustrate writing an essay easier and more accurately.

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